

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Article

Cancer Vaccines

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 27 Mar 2026

Keywords:

Cancer, Vaccines, Anti-cancer vaccines, Cell based, Nucleic acid vaccines

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.19248034

ABSTRACT

Cancer vaccines represent a promising approach in cancer immunotherapy aimed at stimulating the immune system to recognize and eliminate tumor cells. Despite early challenges and limited clinical success, recent advances in tumor genomics, antigen discovery, and vaccine technologies have significantly improved their potential. Personalized vaccines, neoantigen targeting, and mRNA-based platforms offer improved specificity and adaptability to tumor heterogeneity. The use of cancer vaccines in combination with other therapies and in early-stage or adjuvant settings further enhances their effectiveness. Although challenges remain, ongoing research suggests that cancer vaccines may play a vital role in future precision cancer treatment strategies.

INTRODUCTION

Cancer

Cancer is a mysterious and deadly disease of the genome. It is characterized by a genomic instability where a large number of point mutations accumulate and structural alterations occur as the tumour develops in. [1,2]The initial indications of cancer are genetic and epigenetic alterations in specific cells, some of which can spread and migrate to other organs. [3]

Inflammation is a key element of pathophysiology. Cancer can cause inflammation, and inflammation

can encourage cancer growth. A malignant tumor is a colony of cells that can penetrate and spread, grow more often than normal tissue, and multiply uncontrollably. [4] Cancer has been present in multicellular species for more than 200 million years, and there is proof that our ancestors had the disease for more than a million years. [1]

There have been several instances of genetic anomalies that could alter normal human cells and lead to the growth of tumors and cancer. [5]

The primary causes of cancer are mutations that result from anomalies in DNA replication, environmental factors, or inheritance. Aging is the

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

main risk factor for carcinogenesis in humans and other multicellular animals.^[6]

Globally cancer is second major cause of human mortality. In fact, cancer has become more common overall; by 2025 6,18,120 individuals had died from the disease in the United States alone. where it affected over 20,41,910 people. Cancer is therefore a severe issue that has an impact on the wellbeing of all human cultures. Nearly 10 million cancer deaths occurred worldwide in 2020, according to the World Health Organization, and these numbers are predicted to increase as the population ages and grows.

In men, the prostate, colon and rectum, lung and bronchus, and bladder have the largest percentage of cancer kinds. Among women, cancer is most prevalent in the breast, lung and bronchus, colon and rectum, uterine corpus, and thyroid regions. According to this data, a significant percentage of cancers in men and women are caused by prostate and breast cancer, respectively.^[7] Blood cancer, brain cancer, and lymph node cancer are the three cancer kinds that affect youngsters the most frequently.^[8,9]

Conventional methods for treatment of Cancer

A considerable portion of cancer cases can be avoided by taking steps including limiting tobacco use, immunization, early detection, and promoting healthy lifestyles^[10]. The best source of anti-cancer medications is the kingdom of plants. Over 3,000 plant species have been used in cancer treatment and clinical studies to date, and about 30 distinct anti-cancer natural mixtures have been isolated from plants^[6].

In recent decades, medical professionals have discovered more efficient ways to treat it as well as improved techniques for early identification of this terrible illness. However, a cancer cure is 1

years away, and many scientists believe it is unattainable. There are various methods for treating cancer, even though early identification is the best way to prevent it. Among these strategies are:

- Procedure therapy with radiation
- Chemotherapy
- The use of hormones
- Immuno-therapy

Overall, incidence and mortality rates for all four types of cancer in both men and women have steadily declined, with the exception of lung cancer in women. This is likely due to improvements in therapy and combination therapies (surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy, and, more recently, targeted therapy) as well as an increase in early diagnosis. However, despite these positive developments, cancer remains a significant global public health issue that calls for innovative approaches and therapeutic approaches to improve patient outcomes.

The need for more effective cancer treatment methods is highlighted by the significant toxicity and limited applicability of conventional cancer therapies.^[11]

Cancer Vaccines

When most people hear the phrase "vaccine," they think of shots that protect against bacteria and viruses in particular. These vaccines have been shielding humanity from deadly illnesses for a long time.^[12] To prevent or lessen the severity of infectious diseases that can be fatal is the goal of a vaccination prophylactic vaccines). Vaccines frequently produce memory over extended periods of time.^[13] Monoclonal antibodies are currently used in the majority of authorized cancer immunotherapies, however anticancer vaccines are still gaining popularity.^[14]

History of cancer vaccines

There are both therapeutic and preventive vaccinations as excellent cancer immunotherapy approaches. The former aims to prevent illness from a specific malignancy by vaccinating healthy individuals in order to induce immunological memory. Despite years of research and development efforts by numerous academics, the clinical application of cancer vaccines has encountered significant obstacles

The first record of cancer immunotherapy dates back to the 1890s, when Dr. William B. Coley used streptococcal organisms (Coley's toxin) as a therapeutic vaccine in sarcoma patients. [15] Further, Bacillus Calmette Guerin has long been used as a vaccine against tuberculosis and is

being widely utilized as a therapeutic vaccination against bladder cancer. [16, 17]

Types of Cancer vaccines

Anticancer vaccinations can be both remedial and precautionary. The former type seeks to lower the chance of getting cancer. Vaccines against hepatitis B contagion (HBV) and mortal papillomavirus (HPV) are essential anticancer preventative measures. Remedial vaccinations increase vulnerable cells cytotoxic response by promoting their anticancer rates. Remedial vaccinations in discrepancy to the former group, seek to exclude cancer that formerly exists. Multitudinous remedial cancer vaccines have been created over time.

Figure 1. Different types of cancer vaccine

1) Cell based cancer vaccines

The basis of therapeutic cell based vaccines is the in vitro activation of APCs (such as DCs or NK cells) by genes, viral peptides, or genetically altered tumor cells (dead tumor cells). Tumor cell vaccines and immune cell vaccines are two categories of cell-based vaccines. [18] The entire

tumor cell serves as the source of the vaccine in tumor cell vaccines, which include full TAAS, including the epitopes of CD4+ and Cd8-T lymphocytes. Clinical trials for whole-cell cancer vaccines are presently underway. In addition to removing the need to find the perfect target a antigen using whole tumor cells as a vaccine that contains all potential antigens rather than

protein/peptide e tumor antigens also allows for the simultaneous targeting of multiple tumor antigens, which would subsequently trigger additional immune responses to more tumor cells. [19, 20] Vaccines utilizing autologous (patient-specific) or allogeneic (non-patient-specific) tumor cells are the first crucial distinction. Second, these cells can be left unaltered, altered to express MHC, costimulatory molecules, or cytokines, or

combined with adjuvants like Bacille Calmette-Guerin (BCG) and GM-CSF. Third, these cells can be utilized to create tumor-cell lysates. [21] Since this vaccination makes use of tumor cells, it may be able to generate T cells that are specific to any antigen that the cells express. However, this strategy's drawback is that it might occasionally be challenging to gather a sufficient number of cells [22-25].

Figure 2: Mechanism of action of Cell based Cancer Vaccines

DC's that convey antigens to T cells and encourage immune system activation are the subject of a novel therapeutic strategy. Since the late 1990s, DC therapy has been thoroughly researched. [26] When DC's were discovered, Dr. Ralph M. Steinman saw their potential and that DCs may be used as a vaccine. [27] DCs may be loaded with a range of antigens, such as tumor cells, proteins or peptides originating from tumours, and DNA/RNA/virus, could be potentially loaded on DCs. There are additional methods, such as the fusion of DCs with tumor cells. Different types of receptors are present on the surface of dendritic cells (DCs). For example, binding of an antigen to a lectin-like receptor known as scavenger receptor on DCs is reported to induce antigen-specific

suppressive CD4(+) T cells. It is noteworthy that not all antigen presentation by DCs contributes to immune activation [28].

GVAX is a cancer vaccine that uses tumor cells that have been genetically altered to release GM-CSF. It is used to stop the unchecked proliferation of cancer cells following cancer radiotherapy. GM-CSF secretion and patient prognosis have been positively correlated in GVAX phase 1/2 clinical studies for patients with non-small-cell lung cancer [29]. However, phase 3 clinical trials for prostate cancer have not shown any effects. [30].

With encouraging outcomes, a number of phase 2 trials of GVAX therapy for advanced pancreatic cancer have been carried out in conjunction with

body radiation, cyclophosphamide (CY), or the mesothelin expressing *Listeria monocytogenes* vaccination. A combination approach utilizing allogeneic GVAX against metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (CRPC) and an immune checkpoint inhibitor is being investigated, despite the fact that homologous GVAX against CRPC did not meet its phase 3 clinical trial objectives.^[31, 32]

Autologous irradiation tumor cells, either with or without BCG as an adjuvant, make up OncoVAX (Vaccinogen). 254 patients with stage II and III colon cancer were randomly assigned to undergo OncoVAX or no adjuvant treatment following curative removal of the main tumor in a multicenter phase III clinical trial.^[33]

Compared to the control group, patients receiving OncoVAX had a 20.4% lower risk of disease progression throughout the 5.8-year median follow up. A statistically significant improvement in recurrence free survival in stage II was found with a 41.4% decrease in the relative risk of disease progression (P.018) in the OncoVAX. However, analysis by stage revealed no meaningful benefit of OncoVAX in stage III disease. With a relative risk reduction of 11.1% for all patients and 33.3% for stage II patient the OS rate for the OncoVax-treated group was higher than that of the control group.^[34]

DC cancer vaccines are an essential subset of cellular cancer vaccines because of their potent immunogenicity and excellent anti-gen-presenting properties. Neoantigenic cancer vaccines based on personalized DC have recently shown significant anti-tumor activity in clinical settings.^[35-37] For example, patient-derived leukocytes activated in vitro with mesenchymal DC's and a GM-CSF-linked prostatic acid phosphatase (PAP) antigen produce sipuleucel-T, which was licensed by the FDA in 2010 for metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer (mCRPC). Sipuleucel-T showed a

median OS of 25.8 months compared to 21.7 months in the placebo group in the phase III IMPACT study, which included 512 mCRPC patients^[38].

Another autologous tumor lysate-loaded DC vaccine is DCVax L which is noteworthy for its ability to optimize antigen presentation by using tumor lysates to target a broad antigenic library^[39,40,41]. In a phase III trial with patients with recurrent gliomas (r GBM) and newly diagnosed gliomas (nGBM), it demonstrated encouraging efficacy. In particular, among nGBM patients, the median OS was 19.3 months for the DCVax-L group and 16.5 months for the placebo group, with 5-year survival rates of 13.0% and 5.7%, respectively. Furthermore, compared to patients receiving standard medication, those treated with DCVax-L showed a 20% relative reduction in mortality risk over time. The DCVax-L group's median OS for rGBM patients was 13.2 months, while the placebo group's was 7.8 months.^[42]

2) Vaccines based on viral Or bacterial vectors

Developing a way to overcome the host's typically weak immune response against TAAS is one of the main challenges in cancer immunotherapy, as was previously discussed. Recombinant genes, such as those that express TAAs, costimulatory molecules, or cytokines, can be introduced into APCs using a variety of vectors Vaccines based on recombinant vectors may cause the immune system to produce a potent inflammatory response that is primarily focused on vector proteins. An enhanced immune response to the target genes placed into the vector may follow from this inflammatory reaction. One benefit of delivering a recombinant protein using vectors is that it is far more immunogenic than delivering the protein with adjuvants.^[43, 44] Yeast, bacterial, and viral vectors are employed in cancer immunotherapy. Because each vector has unique properties and may be able to stimulate the host

immune system in a different way, the choice of vector can have significant effects on the ensuing immunological response against TAAs.

Viral based vaccines

i) Oncogenic virus vaccines, ii) oncolytic viruses (OVs) and iii) replication defective viral vector vaccines are the three primary categories of virus based immunizations.

Figure 3: Mechanism of action of Viral vector vaccines

i) Oncogenic virus vaccines

Inactivated virus, live attenuated virus, viral subunits, and VLPs are among the various kinds of oncogenic virus based vaccines that are mainly employed in prophylactic contexts. While inactivated viruses are safer but less successful in eliciting cellular immune responses, live attenuated viruses are highly immunogenic but carry hazards of virulence reversal and illness causation in immunocompromised patients.^[45]

Gardasil, Gardasil 9, Cervarix, and Cecolin, which target the HPV L1 epitope, and EngerixB. Recombivax HB, HcpisavB, and PreHevbrio, which target the HBV, are now authorized prophylactic VLP-based cancer vaccines available on market.^[46,47] VIP vaccinations may be used to treat melanoma and HER2positive breast cancer, according to recent research. In a mouse model of

HER2+ mammary cancer, the human HER2 vaccine candidate ES2B-C001 demonstrated potent anti-tumor effectiveness, reaching a 70% tumor-free rate and total suppression of lung metastases^[48].

Preclinical experiments with CMP 001 in situ immunization have demonstrated encouraging tumor control^[49]. In patients with metastatic melanoma, a phase II clinical trial found that CMP001 with pembrolizumab was well tolerated and produced 1800RR.^[50] One problem with viral vectors is that they may express highly immunogenic epitopes, which could prevent some CTL responses against targeted tumor antigens^[51]. Additionally, using alternative vectors or heterologous regimens can address the neutralizing anti-bodies that viral vectors can elicit, which prevent the repeated use of the same vector.^[52]

ii) Replication-defective viral vector-based vaccines.

Target proteins are introduced into the host by replication-defective viral vectors. When coupled with standard treatment, TG4010, a modified vaccinia Ankara (MVA) strain vaccine expressing MUC1 and IL2, significantly improved OS (12.6 vs. 10.6 months) and PFS (5.9 vs 5.1 months) in patients with advanced non small cell lung cancer. [53,54]

In a phase III experiment, Nanofaragene firadenovec, an Ad vaccine that delivers IFNA2B to bladder epithelial cells, produced 53.4% CR within three months of the initial injection, with 45.5 % sustaining response at twelve months [55]. This resulted in its FDA approval in 2022 for the treatment of non-muscle invasive bladder cancer that is not responsive to Bacille Calmette-Guérin (BCG). [56]

Novel approaches have been investigated, such as combination immunizations and heterologous regimens. Research has shown that administering numerous virus vaccines at the same time was both safe and immunogenic. [57, 58]

In a phase II trial of patients with metastatic castration resistant prostate cancer PROSTVAC-VF, a heterologous prime boost regimen using recombinant vaccinia and fowlpox viruses expressing prostate specific antigen (PSA) along with three T-cell costimulatory molecules (B7.1, leukocyte function-associated antigen-3, and intercellular adhesion molecule-1) plus GM-CSF, increased the three-year OS rate (30% vs. 17%) and prolonged PFS or detectable PSA. [59] Because there was no improvement in OS or event free survival the subsequent phase III trial was terminated early. [60] These findings show that replication-defective viral vector-based cancer

vaccines hold potential but need continued exploration to optimize their effectiveness.

iii) Oncolytic virus vaccines

OV vaccines use a natural ability to proliferate in and kill tumor cells, offering a more aggressive but possibly more successful strategy than replication-defective vaccinations, which provide safety by preventing virus replication. [61] Natural viruses are frequently genetically modified by removing unnecessary viral genes and adding target genes, such as cytokines and tumor antigens, to improve tumor targeting and decrease viral pathogenicity. To strengthen anti-tumor immunity, immunomodulatory substances such as GM-CSF, IL-2, IL-18, IFN- γ , and TNF- α have been added to OVs either separately or in combination. [62,63] Four OV vaccines have been authorized thus far for advanced cancer: DELYTACT in 2021, talimogene laherparepvec (T-VEC) in 2015, Rigvir in 2004, and 11101 in 2005. [64]

Although it is not commonly used, rigvir, an unaltered ECHO-7 enterovirus, was approved for melanoma in a number of European nations. Two post-marketing trials revealed that patients with early stage melanoma had longer survival times [65]

H101, an E1B-deleted adenovirus, was approved in China for nasopharyngeal carcinoma after achieving a 78.8% ORR in combination with chemotherapy as opposed to 39.6% with chemotherapy alone. [66] The FDA approved the OV vaccine in 2015 after T-VEC, an attenuated HSV-1 expressing GM-CSF improved median OS (23.3 vs. 18 months) in patients with incurable melanoma. [67,68]

DELYTACT has proven to be effective in treating gliomas. In 12 juvenile patients with recurrent or progressive high-grade glioma, G207, a modified HSV-I with deletions in γ 34.5 and ICP6, extended

the median OS (12.2 vs. 5.6 months)^[69]. The third generation HSV1 vaccine Delytact which was created by removing the a47 gene from parental G207, has been authorized in Japan for the treatment of malignant glioma and may be effective against a number of solid tumors.^[70,71]

Bacterial based vaccines

Traditionally created to prevent infectious diseases, bacteria-based vaccinations have recently surfaced as novel ways to elicit anti-cancer immune responses. Bacillus Calmette-Guérin (BCG) is a prominent example. Originally created as a tuberculosis vaccine, BCG is currently a licensed attenuated bacteria-based immunotherapy (*Mycobacterium bovis*) for the treatment of bladder cancer that is not muscle invasive.^[72,73]

William B. Coley invented the use of microbes for cancer immunotherapy in the late 19 century^[74]. Since then, it has been documented that a number of bacteria specifically colonize tumors and cause immune reactions^[75,76]. Furthermore, a range of pathogen-associated molecular patterns (PAMPs) that might elicit immune responses are present in bacteria and their derivatives^[77]. Additionally, bacteria can be readily altered and loaded with tumor antigens^[78]. Bacteria are a viable platform for anti-cancer vaccine methods because of these features^[79]. Additionally, another intriguing platform for cancer vaccines is the integration of tumor antigens into bacterial outer membrane

vesicles (OMVs) that the host immune system can identify.^[80-83]

However, despite their potential, biosafety issues and the absence of standardized production methods now restrict the clinical translation of bacteria-based immunotherapy^[76].

3) Peptide/protein vaccines.

Immunity against particular antigenic epitopes obtained from the vaccinated protein or peptides that are expressed in cancer cells (and ideally not expressed in normal tissues) can be induced by protein/peptide vaccines. When a synthetic antigen protein or peptide is given, professional APC absorb artificially produced antigen proteins or peptides and present them in combination with the HLA molecules on the cell surface. Immune responses specific to malignancy are triggered when T cells identify the antigens. Numerous antigenic epitopes that can bind HLA and are generated from tumor-associated antigens (TAAs) have been found. Furthermore, neoantigens—antigens produced from cancer-specific gene alterations that are absent from normal tissues—have recently gained interest.^[84-86]

Peptide-based cancer vaccines are very stable, inexpensive to produce, and less harmful. However, they have a number of drawbacks, including as poor immunogenicity, short half-life, degradation susceptibility, and—most importantly—HLA restriction.^[87]

Figure 4 : Mechanism of action of Peptide based Vaccines

In patients with resected colorectal adenoma, a mucin 1 (MUC1) peptide vaccination combined with poly ICLC produced strong immune responses but was unable to stop recurrence^[88]. Similarly, in patients with metastatic or advanced renal cell carcinoma, adding a ten-peptide vaccination with GM-CSF to first-line sunitinib significantly raised the number of CD8⁺ T cells but did not result in clinical benefits.^[89]

In an early phase II trial, OSE2101, which consists of nine peptides that target five TAAs and a pan-DR T helper cell epitope, produced a median survival of 17.3 months in patients with advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC)^[90]. OSE2101 monotherapy later showed superior safety and efficacy over conventional chemotherapy in a larger phase III clinical trial, considerably extending median OS (11.1 vs. 7.5 months) and post progression survival (7.7 vs. 4.6 months) in patients with secondary immunotherapy resistance.^[91]

A number of peptide-based breast cancer vaccines, including the HER2 targeting E75, GP2, and AE37 vaccines, have been thoroughly studied and shown to have therapeutic potential^[92, 93]. In a phase II clinical trial, the E75 vaccination decreased the

recurrence rate in patients with breast cancer; however, in a subsequent phase III trial, the primary survival endpoint was not met.^[94,95] Additionally, in high-risk HER2 low expressing breast cancer, the E75 vaccination plus trastuzumab did not increase disease-free survival (DFS)^[96]. However, sub-group analyses suggested that individuals with HLA-positive or triple-negative breast cancer (TNBC) might benefit^[92,97]

In patients with metastatic melanoma who were not yet receiving anti-PD-1 therapy, 10102-10103, a bispecific vaccination that targets IDO and PDL1, achieved an 80% objective response rate (ORR) and a 25.5-month median progression-free survival (PFS)^[98]. Additionally, individuals with metastatic melanoma are participating in a phase III trial (NC105155254) that looks at the combination of 10102-10103 with pembrolizumab.

4) Nucleic acid based vaccines

By transfecting RNA or DNA into host cells, nucleic acid cancer vaccines that can directly generate the target antigen cause a strong CD8⁺T-cell response mediated by MHC-I molecules^[99].

Usually, there are two types of cancer vaccines: DNA and mRNA.

Figure 5: Mechanism of action of Nucleic acid based Cancer vaccines

DNA based

A new approach that has shown promise in generating robust protection against weak TAAs is DNA-based vaccinations. Improved delivery systems (Gene Gun, cationic liposomes) [100,101], concurrent administration of cytokines (GM-CSF or 12) [102], and the use of distinct plasmids encoding nonself-antigens (such as hepatitis B surface antigen) [103] are some of the strategies that have been developed and tested to increase the potency of DNA-based vaccines. Different changes of plasmid encoded antigens can also increase the immunogenicity of DNA-based vaccinations. [104,105].

One example of a synthetic DNA cancer vaccine is INO-5401, which encodes several cancer antigens, including prostate-specific membrane antigen (PSMA), WT1, and human telomerase reverse transcriptase (HTERT). Reardon et al.'s study of INO-5401 and INO-9012 (a synthetic DNA plasmid encoding interleukin-12 [IL-12]) in glioblastoma patients revealed that this strategy may elicit a robust immune response that is associated with improved survival rates. [106]

GX-188E, a therapeutic HPV E6/E7 DNA vaccination, improved DC antigen processing and presentation when combined with Fms-related tyrosine kinase 3 (Fit3) and the tissue plasminogen activator signal sequence [107]. Patients with grade 3 cervical intraepithelial neoplasia (CIN3) showed strong Th1-polarized cellular immune responses following vaccination, and most of them had particular multifunctional CD8+T cells. [107].

Patients with incurable cervical cancer are presently undergoing a phase II trial to assess the combination of GX-188E with pembrolizumab; the preliminary findings have been encouraging [108].

In patients with proven CIN2/3 intramuscular injection of VGX-3100, which targets HPV E6/E7, followed by electroporation produced a significant histological regression and virus clearance rate. The presence of certain CD8+ T cells, antibody production, and the magnitude of perforin expression were linked to the therapeutic outcomes [109]. Positive outcomes have been reported from the phase III clinical trial of VGX-3100 (NCT03721978).

In patients with advanced hepatocellular carcinoma, GNOS-PV02, another therapeutic DNA vaccine that encoded up to 40 personalized neoantigens and was co-administered with plasmid-encoded IL-12 plus pembrolizumab, produced a 30.6% ORR and an 8.3% complete response (CR).^[110]

RNA based

Another appealing therapeutic strategy for the treatment of cancer is mRNA-based gene transfer vaccines^[111, 112]. Because the transfected mRNA does not integrate into the host genome, this technique, which is mainly based on transitory transfection of nondividing cells, is considered pharmaceutically safe^[113]. Additionally, electroporation can be used to obtain high transfection efficiency. In vitro transcription from a bacteriophage promoter-equipped plasmid DNA produces mRNA, which can be efficiently overexpressed in target cells. It consists of a polyadenosine tail (polyA tail), the target antigen's coding RNA, and a cap structure at the 5' end.^[114,115,116]

The target antigen may be autologous tumor mRNA^[121], allogeneic cancer cell lines^[130, 119, 120], or a single peptide PSA^[117] or CEA^[118]. After being transfected into DCs, the mRNA-based vaccine carrying the mRNA-coding TAA is translated into proteins. An antigen-specific CTL response can be triggered by loading the antigen onto MHC molecules for antigen presentation following protein processing.^[122]

Patients with prostate cancer^[130,117,123] RCC^[124] ovarian cancer^[125] lung cancer breast cancer^[118], pediatric brain cancer^[126], neuroblastoma^[127], and melanoma^[128, 129] have undergone clinical trials using mRNA-transfected DCs or directly injecting mRNA. PSA-mRNA-transfected DCs were used in a phase I clinical trial for patients with

metastatic prostate cancer^[117]. The results showed that the vaccine could boost PSA-specific CTL responses when the effects of repeated immunizations with PSA-mRNA-transfected DCs were investigated.

Future Prospects of Cancer Vaccines

Cancer vaccines are emerging as an important area of research in modern oncology, with a growing focus on personalized and precision-based treatment strategies. Rapid progress in tumor genomics and molecular profiling has made it possible to identify tumor-specific antigens unique to each patient. This has encouraged the development of personalized cancer vaccines that can stimulate a targeted immune response against cancer cells while sparing healthy tissues.

Neoantigen-based vaccines represent one of the most promising advancements in this field. Since neoantigens arise from tumor-specific mutations, they are highly immunogenic and reduce the risk of immune tolerance. In addition, the development of mRNA and DNA vaccine platforms has further strengthened cancer vaccine research. These platforms allow rapid production, flexibility in antigen selection, and the inclusion of multiple antigens within a single formulation, making them well suited to address tumor heterogeneity.

Another important future direction is the use of cancer vaccines in combination with other treatment modalities. When used alongside immune checkpoint inhibitors, chemotherapy, radiotherapy, or targeted therapies, cancer vaccines may enhance immune activation and improve therapeutic outcomes. Such combination approaches can help overcome immune suppression created by the tumor microenvironment. Clinical research is also shifting toward the use of cancer vaccines in early-stage disease and adjuvant settings, particularly

after surgical removal of tumors. At this stage, the immune system is better equipped to respond, increasing the chances of preventing recurrence. Additionally, targeting cancer stem cells and circulating tumor cells through vaccination strategies may reduce metastasis and long-term relapse. The identification of reliable biomarkers and improved immune monitoring techniques will further guide patient selection, treatment optimization, and assessment of vaccine efficacy. Together, these advancements suggest that cancer vaccines may play a more significant role in future cancer management.

CONCLUSION

Although the development of cancer vaccines has faced several setbacks in the past, recent scientific advances have renewed confidence in this therapeutic approach. Earlier challenges, such as tumor heterogeneity, inadequate antigen selection, and use in late-stage disease, limited their clinical success. However, improved understanding of tumor biology and immune mechanisms has highlighted the importance of personalized, multi-antigen, and combination-based vaccine strategies. The future of cancer vaccines lies in individualized treatment, early clinical application, and integration with other cancer therapies. Despite challenges related to manufacturing, cost, and regulatory approval, cancer vaccines hold strong potential as a safe and targeted treatment option with continued research and technological progress, they are likely to become an important component of precision oncology.

REFERENCES

1. Hausman DM. What is cancer? *Perspect Biol Med.* 2019;62(4):778–784.
2. Zhang Y, Zhang Z. The history and advances in cancer immunotherapy: understanding the

characteristics of tumor-infiltrating immune cells and their therapeutic implications. *Cell Mol Immunol.* 2020;17(8):807–821.

3. Piña-Sánchez P, Chávez-González A, Ruiz-Tachiquín M, Vadillo-Monroy-García A, Montesinos JJ, Grajales R, et al. Cancer biology, epidemiology, and treatment in the 21st century: current status and future challenges from a biomedical perspective. *Cancer Control.* 2021;28:10732748211038735.
4. Vaghari-Tabari M, Ferns GA, Qujeq D, Andevari AN, Sabahi Z, Moein S. Signaling, metabolism, and cancer: an important relationship for therapeutic intervention. *J Cell Physiol.* 2021;236(8):5512–5532.
5. Upadhyay A. Cancer: an unknown territory; rethinking before ahead. *Genes Dis.* 2020;8(5):655–661.
6. Hazafa A, Rehman KU, Jahan N, Jabeen Z. The role of polyphenol (flavonoids) compounds in the treatment of cancer cells. *Nutr Cancer.* 2020;72(3):386–397.
7. Siegel RL, Miller KD, Jemal A. Cancer statistics, 2016. *CA Cancer J Clin.* 2016;66(1):7–30.
8. Schottenfeld D, Fraumeni JF Jr. *Cancer epidemiology and prevention.* 3rd ed. Oxford: Oxford University Press; 2006.
9. Yoo KY, Shin HR. Cancer epidemiology and prevention. *Korean J Epidemiol.* 2003;25(1):1–15.
10. Torre LA, Siegel RL, Ward EM, Jemal A. Global cancer incidence and mortality rates and trends—an update. *Cancer Epidemiol Biomarkers Prev.* 2016;25(1):16–27.
11. Mazzayeni R, et al. What are the reasons for continuing failures in cancer therapy? Are misleading/inappropriate preclinical assays to be blamed? Might some modern therapies cause more harm than benefit? *Int J Mol Sci.* 2022;23(2):—.

12. World Health Organization. Assessment reports of the Global Vaccine Action Plan. Geneva: WHO; 2018.
13. Sallusto F, Lanzavecchia A, Araki K, Ahmed R. From vaccines to memory and back. *Immunity*. 2010;33(4):451–463.
14. Paul S, Konig MF, Pardoll DM, Bettegowda C, Papadopoulos N, Wright KM, et al. Cancer therapy with antibodies. *Nat Rev Cancer*. 2024;24:399–426.
15. Coley WB. Contribution to the knowledge of sarcoma. *Ann Surg*. 1891;14(3):199–220.
16. Bacillus Calmette-Guérin in the treatment of superficial bladder tumors. *J Urol*. 1976;116(2):180–182.
17. Kamat AM, Bellmunt J, Galsky MD, et al. Society for Immunotherapy of Cancer consensus statement on immunotherapy for the treatment of bladder carcinoma. *J Immunother Cancer*. 2017;5(1):68.
18. Keenan BP, Jaffee EM. Whole cell vaccines—past progress and future strategies. *Semin Oncol*. 2012;39(3):276–286.
19. Bencherif SA, Sands RW, Ali OA, Li WA, Lewin SA, Braschler TM, et al. Injectable cryogel-based whole-cell cancer vaccines. *Nat Commun*. 2015;6:7556.
20. Chiang CL, Benencia F, Coukos G. Whole tumor antigen vaccines. *Semin Immunol*. 2010;22(3):132–143.
21. Copier J, Dalgleish A. Overview of tumor cell-based vaccines. *Int Rev Immunol*. 2006;25(5-6):297–319.
22. Berger M, Kreutz FT, Horst JL, Baldi AC, Koff WJ. Phase I study with an autologous tumor cell vaccine for locally advanced or metastatic prostate cancer. *J Pharm Pharm Sci*. 2007;10(2):144–152.
23. Harris JE, Ryan L, Hoover HC Jr, et al. Adjuvant active specific immunotherapy for stage II and III colon cancer with an autologous tumor cell vaccine: Eastern Cooperative Oncology Group Study E5283. *J Clin Oncol*. 2000;18(1):148–157.
24. Mayer C, McKneally MF. Preparation of autologous tumor cell vaccine from human lung cancer. *Cancer Res*. 1979;39(8):3237–3243.
25. Schult RS, Mai D, Nelson MA, et al. Active specific immunotherapy with an autologous tumor cell vaccine in patients with resected non-small-cell lung cancer. *Mol Biother*. 1988;1(1):30–36.
26. Nestle FO, Alijagic S, Gilliet M, et al. Vaccination of melanoma patients with peptide- or tumor lysate-pulsed dendritic cells. *Nat Med*. 1998;4(3):328–332.
27. Steinman RM, Banchereau J. Taking dendritic cells into medicine. *Nature*. 2007;449(7161):419–426.
28. Li D, Romain G, Flamar AL, et al. Targeting self- and foreign antigens to dendritic cells via DC-ASGPR generates IL-10-producing suppressive CD4+ T cells. *J Exp Med*. 2012;209(1):109–121.
29. Nemunaitis J, Jahan T, Ross H, et al. Phase 1/2 trial of autologous tumor mixed with an allogeneic GVAX® vaccine in advanced-stage non-small-cell lung cancer. *Cancer Gene Ther*. 2006;13(6):555–562.
30. Arlen PM, Mohebtash M, Madan RA, Gulley JL. Promising novel immunotherapies and combinations for prostate cancer. *Future Oncol*. 2009;5(2):187–196.
31. van den Eertwegh AJM, Versluis J, van den Berg HP, et al. Combined immunotherapy with GM-CSF-transduced allogeneic prostate cancer cells and ipilimumab in metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer: a phase I dose-escalation trial. *Lancet Oncol*. 2012;13(5):509–517.

32. Wang XY, Zuo D, Sarkar D, Fisher PB. Blockade of cytotoxic T-lymphocyte antigen-4 as a new therapeutic approach for advanced melanoma. *Expert Opin Pharmacother.* 2011;12(17):2695–2706.
33. Vermorken JB, Claessen AME, van Tinteren H, et al. Active specific immunotherapy for stage II and stage III human colon cancer: a randomised trial. *Lancet.* 1999;353(9150):345–350.
34. Uyl-de Groot CA, Vermorken JB, Hanna MG Jr, et al. Immunotherapy with autologous tumor cell-BCG vaccine in patients with colon cancer: a prospective study of medical and economic benefits. *Vaccine.* 2005;23(17–18):2379–2387.
35. Santos PM, Butterfield LH. Dendritic cell-based cancer vaccines. *J Immunol.* 2018;200(2):443–449. doi:10.4049/jimmunol.1701024
36. Perez CR, De Palma M. Engineering dendritic cell vaccines to improve cancer immunotherapy. *Nat Commun.* 2019;10:5408. doi:10.1038/s41467-019-13368-y
37. Garg AD, Vandenberk L, Koks C, Verschuere T, Boon L, Van Gool SW, et al. Dendritic cell vaccines based on immunogenic cell death elicit danger signals and T-cell-driven rejection of high-grade glioma. *Sci Transl Med.* 2016;8(328):328ra27. doi:10.1126/scitranslmed.aad0105
38. Kantoff PW, Higano CS, Shore ND, et al. Sipuleucel-T immunotherapy for castration-resistant prostate cancer. *N Engl J Med.* 2010;363(5):411–422. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa1001294
39. Liau LM, Prins RM, Kiertscher SM, et al. Dendritic cell vaccination in glioblastoma patients induces systemic and intracranial T-cell responses modulated by the local central nervous system tumor microenvironment. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2005;11(15):5515–5525.
40. Prins RM, Cloughesy TF, Liau LM. Cytomegalovirus immunity after vaccination with autologous glioblastoma lysate. *N Engl J Med.* 2008;359:539–41. doi:10.1056/NEJMc0804818.
41. Prins RM, Soto H, Konkankit V, Odesa SK, Eskin A, Yong WH, et al. Gene expression profile correlates with T-cell infiltration and relative survival in glioblastoma patients vaccinated with dendritic cell immunotherapy. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2011;17:1603–15. doi:10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-10-2563.
42. Liau LM, Ashkan K, Brem S, Campian JL, Trusheim JE, Iwamoto FM, et al. Association of autologous tumor lysate-loaded dendritic cell vaccination with extension of survival among patients with newly diagnosed and recurrent glioblastoma: a phase 3 prospective externally controlled cohort trial. *JAMA Oncol.* 2023;9:112–21.
43. Lechleider RJ, Arlen PM, Tsang KY, et al. Safety and immunologic response of a viral vaccine to prostate-specific antigen in combination with radiation therapy when metronomic-dose interleukin-2 is used as an adjuvant. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2008;14(16):5284–91.
44. Kantor J, Abrams S, Irvine K, Snoy P, Kaufman H, Schlom J. Specific immunotherapy using a recombinant vaccinia virus expressing human carcinoembryonic antigen. *Ann N Y Acad Sci.* 1993;690:370–3.
45. Ghattas M, Dwivedi G, Lavertu M, Alameh MG. Vaccine technologies and platforms for infectious diseases: current progress, challenges, and opportunities. *Vaccines.*

- 2021;9:21490.
doi:10.3390/vaccines9121490.
46. Mohsen MO, Bachmann MF. Virus-like particle vaccinology, from bench to bedside. *Cell Mol Immunol.* 2022;19(9):993–1011. doi:10.1038/s41423-022-00897-8.
 47. Huh WK, Joura EA, Giuliano AR, et al. Final efficacy, immunogenicity, and safety analyses of a nine-valent human papillomavirus vaccine in women aged 16–26 years: a randomised, double-blind trial. *Lancet.* 2017;390(10108):2143–59. doi:10.1016/S0140-6736(17)31821-4.
 48. Ruzzi F, Palladini A, Clemmensen S, et al. Prevention and therapy of metastatic HER-2-positive mammary carcinoma with a human candidate HER-2 virus-like particle vaccine. *Biomedicines.* 2022;10:2654. doi:10.3390/biomedicines10102654.
 49. Cheng Y, Lemke-Milner CD, Wongpatarawakul W, et al. In situ immunization of a TLR9 agonist virus-like particle enhances anti-PD-1 therapy. *J Immunother Cancer.* 2020. doi:10.1136/jitc-2020-000940.
 50. Milhem M, Zakharia Y, Dayar D, et al. Durable responses in anti-PD-1-refractory melanoma following intratumoral injection of a toll-like receptor 9 agonist, CMP-001, in combination with pembrolizumab. *J Immunother Cancer.* 2020;8(Suppl 1):A2–3. doi:10.1136/LBA2019-4.
 51. Smith CL, Mirza F, Pasquetto V, et al. Immunodominance of poxviral-specific CTL in a human trial of recombinant-modified vaccinia Ankara. *J Immunol.* 2005;175(12):8431–7. doi:10.4049/jimmunol.175.12.8431.
 52. Bonilla WV, Kirchhammer N, Marx AF, et al. Heterologous arenavirus vector prime-boost overrules self-tolerance for efficient tumor-specific CD8 T-cell attack. *Cell Rep Med.* 2021;2:100209. doi:10.1016/j.xcrm.2021.100209.
 53. Quoix E, Lena H, Losonczy G, et al. TG4010 immunotherapy and first-line chemotherapy for advanced non-small-cell lung cancer (TIME): results from the phase 2b part of a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled, phase 2b/3 trial. *Lancet Oncol.* 2016;17(2):212–23. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(15)00483-0.
 54. Tosch C, Bastien B, Barraud L, et al. Viral-based vaccine TG4010 induces broadening of specific immune response and improves outcome in advanced NSCLC. *J Immunother Cancer.* 2017;5(1):70. doi:10.1186/s40425-017-0274-x.
 55. Boorjian SA, Alemozaffar M, Konety BR, et al. Intravesical nadofaragene firadenovec gene therapy for BCG-unresponsive non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer: a single-arm, open-label, repeat-dose clinical trial. *Lancet Oncol.* 2021;22(1):107–17. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(20)30540-4.
 56. Sahlhout SZ, Miller DM, Emerick KS, Kaufman HL. Therapy with oncolytic viruses: progress and challenges. *Nat Rev Clin Oncol.* 2023;20(3):160–77. doi:10.1038/s41571-022-00719-w.
 57. Gatti-Mays ME, Redman JM, Donahue RN, et al. A phase I trial using a multitargeted recombinant adenovirus 5 (CEA/MUC1/Brachyury)-based immunotherapy vaccine regimen in patients with advanced cancer. *Oncologist.* 2020;25(6):479–e899. doi:10.1634/theoncologist.2019-0608.
 58. Bilusic M, McMahon S, Madan RA, et al. Phase I study of a multitargeted recombinant Ad5 PSA/MUC-1/brachyury-based immunotherapy vaccine in patients with metastatic castration-resistant prostate

- cancer (mCRPC). *J Immunother Cancer*. 2021. doi:10.1136/jitc-2021-002374
59. Kantoff PW, Schuetz TJ, Blumenstein BA, et al. Overall survival analysis of a phase II randomized controlled trial of a poxviral-based PSA-targeted immunotherapy in metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer. *J Clin Oncol*. 2010;28(7):1099–1105. doi:10.1200/JCO.2009.25.0597
 60. Gulley JL, Borre M, Vogelzang NJ, et al. Phase III trial of PROSTVAC in asymptomatic or minimally symptomatic metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer. *J Clin Oncol*. 2019;37(13):1051–1061. doi:10.1200/JCO.18.02031
 61. Ma R, Li Z, Chiocca EA, Caligiuri MA, Yu J. The emerging field of oncolytic virus-based cancer immunotherapy. *Trends Cancer*. 2023;9(2):122–139. doi:10.1016/j.trecan.2022.10.003
 62. Li X, Lu M, Yuan M, et al. CXCL10-armed oncolytic adenovirus promotes tumor-infiltrating T-cell chemotaxis to enhance anti-PD-1 therapy. *Oncoimmunology*. 2022;11(1):2118210. doi:10.1080/2162402X.2022.2118210
 63. Macedo N, Miller DM, Haq R, Kaufman HL. Clinical landscape of oncolytic virus research in 2020. *J Immunother Cancer*. 2020. doi:10.1136/jitc-2020-001486
 64. Hietanen E, Koivu MKA, Susi P. Cytolytic properties and genome analysis of Rigvir® oncolytic virotherapy virus and other echovirus 7 isolates. *Viruses*. 2022. doi:10.3390/v14030525
 65. Xia ZJ, Chang JH, Zhang L, et al. Phase III randomized clinical trial of intratumoral injection of E1B gene-deleted adenovirus (H101) combined with cisplatin-based chemotherapy in treating squamous cell cancer of head and neck or esophagus. *Ai Zheng*. 2004;23(12):1666–1670.
 66. Andtbacka RH, Kaufman HL, Collichio F, et al. Talimogene laherparepvec improves durable response rate in patients with advanced melanoma. *J Clin Oncol*. 2015;33(25):2780–2788. doi:10.1200/JCO.2014.58.3377
 67. Andtbacka RH, Collichio F, Harrington KJ, et al. Final analyses of OPTIM: a randomized phase III trial of talimogene laherparepvec versus granulocyte-macrophage colony-stimulating factor in unresectable stage IIIB–IV melanoma. *J Immunother Cancer*. 2019;7(1):145. doi:10.1186/s40425-019-0623-z
 68. Friedman GK, Johnston JM, Bag AK, et al. Oncolytic HSV-1 G207 immunovirotherapy for pediatric high-grade gliomas. *N Engl J Med*. 2021;384(17):1613–1622. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa2024947
 69. Todo T, Ito H, Ino Y, et al. Intratumoral oncolytic herpes virus G47Δ for residual or recurrent glioblastoma: a phase II trial. *Nat Med*. 2022;28(8):1630–1639. doi:10.1038/s41591-022-01897-x
 70. Todo T, Ino Y, Ohtsu H, Shibahara J, Tanaka M. A phase I/II study of triple-mutated oncolytic herpes virus G47Δ in patients with progressive glioblastoma. *Nat Commun*. 2022;13(1):4119. doi:10.1038/s41467-022-31262-y
 71. Cardillo F, Bonfim M, da Silva Vasconcelos Sousa P, Mengel J, Ribeiro Castelo-Branco LR, Pinho RT. Bacillus calmette-guérin immunotherapy for cancer. *Vaccines (Basel)*. 2021;9(5).
 72. Cardillo F, Bonfim M, da Silva Vasconcelos Sousa P, Mengel J, Ribeiro Castelo-Branco LR, Pinho RT. Bacillus Calmette-Guérin immunotherapy for cancer. *Vaccines (Basel)*. 2021;9(5):—.
 73. Sylvester RJ, van der Meijden APM, Lamm DL. Intravesical bacillus Calmette-Guérin

- reduces the risk of progression in patients with superficial bladder cancer: a meta-analysis of the published results of randomized clinical trials. *J Urol.* 2002;168(5):1964-1970.
74. Coley WB. The treatment of inoperable sarcoma with the mixed toxins of erysipelas and *Bacillus prodigiosus*: immediate and final results in one hundred and forty cases. *J Am Med Assoc.* 1898;31(9):456-465.
 75. Zheng JH, Nguyen VH, Jiang SN, Park SH, Tan W, Hong SH, et al. Two-step enhanced cancer immunotherapy with engineered *Salmonella Typhimurium* secreting heterologous flagellin. *Sci Transl Med.* 2017;9(376).
 76. Zhou M, Tang Y, Xu W, Hao X, Li Y, Huang S, et al. Bacteria-based immunotherapy for cancer: a systematic review of preclinical studies. *Front Immunol.* 2023;14:1140463.
 77. Yaghoubi A, Khazaei M, Jalili S, Hasanian SM, Avan A, Soleimanpour S, et al. Bacteria as a double-action sword in cancer. *Biochim Biophys Acta Rev Cancer.* 2020;1874(1):188388.
 78. Chen Z, Yong T, Wei Z, Zhang X, Li X, Qin J, et al. Engineered probiotic-based personalized cancer vaccine potentiates antitumor immunity through initiating trained immunity. *Adv Sci (Weinh).* 2024;11(3):e2305081.
 79. Derré L, Cesson V, Lucca L, Cerantola Y, Valerio M, Fritschi U, et al. Intravesical *Bacillus Calmette–Guérin* combined with a cancer vaccine increases local T-cell responses in non-muscle-invasive bladder cancer patients. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2017;23(3):717-725.
 80. Caproni E, Corbellari R, Tomasi M, Isaac SJ, Tamburini S, Zanella I, et al. Anti-tumor efficacy of in situ vaccination using bacterial outer membrane vesicles. *Cancers (Basel).* 2023;15(13):—.
 81. Cheng K, Zhao R, Li Y, Qi Y, Wang Y, Zhang Y, et al. Bioengineered bacteria-derived outer membrane vesicles as a versatile antigen display platform for tumour vaccination via plug-and-display technology. *Nat Commun.* 2021;12(1):2041.
 82. Tamburini S, Zhang Y, Gagliardi A, Di Lasco G, Caproni E, Benedet M, et al. Bacterial outer membrane vesicles as a platform for the development of a broadly protective human papillomavirus vaccine based on the minor capsid protein L2. *Vaccines (Basel).* 2023;11(10):—.
 83. Wang S, Guo J, Bai Y, Sun C, Wu Y, Liu Z, et al. Bacterial outer membrane vesicles as a candidate tumor vaccine platform. *Front Immunol.* 2022;13:987419.
 84. Meena N, Mathur P, Medicherla KM, Suravajhala P. A bioinformatics pipeline for whole exome sequencing: overview of the processing and steps from raw data to downstream analysis. *bioRxiv.* 2021.
 85. Tsoi LC, Wolf B, Chen YA. The promise of genomic studies on human diseases: from basic science to clinical application. *Int J Genomics.* 2017;2017:7983236.
 86. Roudko V, Greenbaum B, Bhardwaj N. Computational prediction and validation of tumor-associated neoantigens. *Front Immunol.* 2020;11:27
 87. Peres Lde P, da Luz FA, Pultz Bdos A, et al. Peptide vaccines in breast cancer: the immunological basis for clinical response. *Biotechnol Adv.* 2015;33(8):1868–1877.
 88. Schoen RE, Boardman LA, Cruz-Correa M, et al. Randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial of MUC1 peptide vaccine for prevention of recurrent colorectal adenoma. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2023;29(9):1678–1688. Doi:10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-22-3168

89. Rini BI, Stenzl A, Zdrojowy R, et al. IMA901, a multi-peptide cancer vaccine, plus sunitinib versus sunitinib alone, as first-line therapy for advanced or metastatic renal cell carcinoma (IMPRINT): a multicentre, open-label, randomised, controlled, phase 3 trial. *Lancet Oncol.* 2016;17(11):1599–1611.
90. Besse B, Charrier M, Laplanche A, et al. Induction of immune responses and clinical efficacy in a phase II trial of IDM-2101, a 10-epitope cytotoxic T-lymphocyte vaccine, in metastatic non-small-cell lung cancer. *J Clin Oncol.* 2008;26(27):4418–4425. Doi:10.1200/JCO.2008.16.6462
91. Besse B, Felip E, Garcia-Campelo R, et al. Randomized open-label controlled study of cancer vaccine OSE2101 versus chemotherapy in HLA-A2-positive patients with advanced non-small-cell lung cancer with resistance to immunotherapy: ATALANTE 1. *Ann Oncol.* 2023;34(10):920–933.
92. Brown TA, Mittendorf EA, Hale DF, et al. Prospective, randomized, single-blinded, multicenter phase II trial of two HER2 peptide vaccines, GP2 and AE37, in breast cancer patients to prevent recurrence. *Breast Cancer Res Treat.* 2020;181(2):391–401. Doi:10.1007/s10549-020-05638-x
93. Patel S, McWilliams D, Fischer T, Thompson J, Patel M, Daugherty F. Final five-year median follow-up safety data from a prospective, randomized, placebo-controlled, single-blinded, multicenter phase IIb study evaluating the use of HER2/neu peptide GP2+GM-CSF vs GM-CSF alone after adjuvant trastuzumab in HER2-positive women with operable breast cancer. *J Clin Oncol.* 2021;39(15 suppl):542–542. Doi:10.1200/JCO.2021.39.15_suppl.542
94. Mittendorf EA, Clifton GT, Holmes JP, et al. Final report of the phase VII clinical trial of the E75 (nelipepimut-S) vaccine with booster inoculations to prevent disease recurrence in high-risk breast cancer patients. *Ann Oncol.* 2014;25(9):1735–1742. Doi:10.1093/annonc/mdu211
95. Mittendorf EA, Lu R, Melisko M, et al. Efficacy and safety analysis of nelipepimut-S vaccine to prevent breast cancer recurrence: a randomized, multicenter, phase III clinical trial. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2019;25(14):4748–4754. Doi:10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-18-2867
96. Clifton GT, Hale D, Vreeland TJ, et al. Results of a randomized phase IIb trial of nelipepimut-S plus trastuzumab versus trastuzumab to prevent recurrences in patients with high-risk HER2 low-expressing breast cancer. *Clin Cancer Res.* 2020;26(11):2515–2523. Doi:10.1158/1078-0432.CCR-19-2741
97. Chick RC, Clifton GT, Hale DF, et al. Subgroup analysis of nelipepimut-S plus GM-CSF combined with trastuzumab versus trastuzumab alone to prevent recurrences in patients with high-risk, HER2 low-expressing breast cancer. *Clin Immunol.* 2021;225:108679.
98. Lorentzen C, Kjeldsen JW, Ehrnrooth E, Andersen MH, Marie Svanø J. Long-term follow-up of anti-PD-1-naïve patients with metastatic melanoma treated with IDO/PD-L1 targeting peptide vaccine and nivolumab. *J Immunother Cancer.* 2023;11:e006873.
99. Sobhan N, Scaggiante B, Morris R, Chai D, Catalano M, Tardiel-Cyril DR, et al. Therapeutic cancer vaccines: from biological mechanisms and engineering to ongoing clinical trials. *Cancer Treat Rev.* 2022;109:102429.
100. Best SR, Peng S, Juang CM, et al. Administration of HPV DNA vaccine via electroporation elicits the strongest CD8+ T-

- cell immune responses compared to intramuscular injection and intradermal gene gun delivery. *Vaccine*. 2009;27(40):5450–5459.
101. en L, Kell R, Dow SW. Vaccination with liposome–DNA complexes elicits enhanced antitumor immunity. *Cancer Gene Ther*. 2006;13(11):1033–1044.
 102. Pasquini S, Xiang Z, Wang Y, et al. Cytokines and costimulatory molecules as genetic adjuvants. *Immunol Cell Biol*. 1997;75(4):397–401.
 103. Cong RM, Curiel DT, Strong TV, et al. Safety and immunogenicity of a DNA vaccine encoding ganglioside tumor antigen and hepatitis B surface antigen in colorectal carcinoma patients. *Clin Cancer Res*. 2002;8(9):2782–2787.
 104. Binder RJ, Srivastava PK. Peptides chaperoned by heat-shock proteins are necessary and sufficient source of antigen in the cross-priming of CD8⁺ T cells. *Nat Immunol*. 2005;6(6):593–599.
 105. Segal BH, Wang XY, Dennis CG, et al. Heat shock proteins as vaccine adjuvants in infections and cancer. *Drug Discov Today*. 2006;11(11–12):534–540.
 106. Reardon DA, Brem S, Desai AS, Bagley SJ, Kurz SC, De La Fuente MI, et al. Intramuscular INO-5401 and INO-9012 with electroporation in combination with cemiplimab in newly diagnosed glioblastoma. *J Clin Oncol*. 2022;40(16 Suppl):2004. doi:10.1200/JCO.2022.40.16_suppl.2004.
 107. Kim TJ, Jin HT, Hur SY, et al. Clearance of persistent HPV infection and cervical lesions by therapeutic DNA vaccine in CIN3 patients. *Nat Commun*. 2014;5:5317. doi:10.1038/ncomms6317.
 108. Youn JW, Hur SY, Woo JW, et al. Pembrolizumab plus GX-188E therapeutic DNA vaccine in patients with HPV-16– or HPV-18–positive advanced cervical cancer: interim results of a phase II trial. *Lancet Oncol*. 2020;21(12):1653–1660. doi:10.1016/S1470-2045(20)30486-1.
 109. Trimble CL, Morrow MP, Kraynyak KA, et al. Safety, efficacy, and immunogenicity of VGX-3100, a therapeutic DNA vaccine targeting HPV-16 and HPV-18 E6/E7 proteins for CIN 2/3: a randomized, double-blind, placebo-controlled phase 2b trial. *Lancet*. 2015;386(10008):2078–2088.
 110. Yarchoan M, Gane EJ, Maron TU, et al. Personalized neoantigen vaccine and pembrolizumab in advanced hepatocellular carcinoma: a phase I trial. *Nat Med*. 2024.
 111. Kyte JA, Gaudernack G. Immunogene therapy of cancer with tumour mRNA-transfected dendritic cells. *Cancer Immunol Immunother*. 2006;55(11):1432–1442.
 112. Weide B, Garbe C, Rammensee HG, Pascolo S. Plasmid DNA- and messenger RNA-based anticancer vaccination. *Immunol Lett*. 2008;115(1):33–42.
 113. Yamamoto A, Kormann M, Rosenecker J, Rudolph C. Current prospects for mRNA gene delivery. *Eur J Pharm Biopharm*. 2009;71(3):484–489.
 114. Van Tendeloo VF, Ponsaerts P, Lardon F, et al. Highly efficient gene delivery by mRNA electroporation in human hematopoietic cells. *Blood*. 2001;98(1):49–56.
 115. Ponsaerts P, Van der Sar S, Van Tendeloo VF, Jorens PG, Berneman ZN, Singh PB. Highly efficient mRNA-based gene transfer in feeder-free cultured H9 human embryonic stem cells. *Cloning Stem Cells*. 2004;6(3):211–216.
 116. Krieg PA, Melton DA. Functional messenger RNAs are produced by SP6 in vitro transcription of cloned DNAs. *Nucleic Acids Res*. 1984;12(18):7057–7070.

117. Heiser A, Coleman D, Dannull J, et al. Autologous dendritic cells transfected with prostate-specific antigen RNA stimulate CTL responses against metastatic prostate tumors. *J Clin Invest.* 2002;109(3):409–417.
118. Morse MA, Nair SK, Mosca PJ, et al. Immunotherapy with autologous human dendritic cells transfected with carcinoembryonic antigen mRNA. *Cancer Invest.* 2003;21(3):341–349.
119. Hirschowitz EA, Foody T, Kryscio R, Dickson L, Sturgill J, Yannelli JR. Autologous dendritic cell vaccines for non-small-cell lung cancer. *J Clin Oncol.* 2004;22(14):2808–2815.
120. Pandha HS, John RJ, Hutchinson J, et al. Dendritic cell immunotherapy for urological cancers using cryopreserved allogeneic tumour lysate-pulsed cells: a phase I/II study. *BJU Int.* 2004;93(3):412–418.
121. Kyte JA, Kvalheim G, Aamdal S, Sæbøe-Larssen S, Gaudernack G. Preclinical full-scale evaluation of dendritic cells transfected with autologous tumor mRNA for melanoma vaccination. *Cancer Gene Ther.* 2005;12(6):545–559.
122. Pascolo S. Messenger RNA-based vaccines. *Expert Opin Biol Ther.* 2004;4(8):1285–1294.
123. Su Z, Dannull J, Yang BK, et al. Telomerase mRNA-transfected dendritic cells stimulate antigen-specific CD8⁺ and CD4⁺ T-cell responses in patients with metastatic prostate cancer. *J Immunol.* 2005;174(6):3798–3807.
124. Su Z, Dannull J, Heiser A, et al. Immunological and clinical responses in metastatic renal cancer patients vaccinated with tumor RNA-transfected dendritic cells. *Cancer Res.* 2003;63(9):2127–2133.
125. Dannull J, Su Z, Rizzieri D, et al. Enhancement of vaccine-mediated antitumor immunity in cancer patients after depletion of regulatory T cells. *J Clin Invest.* 2005;115(12):3623–3633.
126. Caruso DA, Orme LM, Neale AM, et al. Results of a phase I study utilizing monocyte-derived dendritic cells pulsed with tumor RNA in children and young adults with brain cancer. *Neuro Oncol.* 2004;6(3):236–246.
127. Caruso DA, Orme LM, Amor GM, et al. Results of a phase I study utilizing monocyte-derived dendritic cells pulsed with tumor RNA in children with stage 4 neuroblastoma. *Cancer.* 2005;103(6):1280–1291.
128. Kyte JA, Mu L, Aamdal S, et al. Phase II trial of melanoma therapy with dendritic cells transfected with autologous tumor mRNA. *Cancer Gene Ther.* 2006;13(10):905–918.
129. Weide B, Pascolo S, Scheel B, et al. Direct injection of protamine-protected mRNA: results of a phase I vaccination trial in metastatic melanoma patients. *J Immunother.* 2009;32(5):498–507.
130. Mu LJ, Kyte JA, Kvalheim G, et al. Immunotherapy with allotumour mRNA-transfected dendritic cells in androgen-resistant prostate cancer patients. *Br J Cancer.* 2005;93(7):749–756.

HOW TO CITE: Ashwini Taware, Chetana Mayekar, Manisha Nangude, Harsh Tapal, Pranali Vekhande, Manas Suryarao, Cancer Vaccines, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 3, 3632-3651. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19248034>

